

Optically Active Aliphatic Thioesters from S-(+)-2-Methylbutan-1-thiol

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Optically active aliphatic thioesters of the type,

where R = methyl, ethyl, n-propyl, n-butyl, n-amyl, n-hexyl, n-heptyl and n-nonyl have been prepared by the condensation of optically active S-(+)-2-methylbutan-1-thiol and various aliphatic acid halides. The optical rotation and infrared spectra of these thioesters have been studied.

P RATT and Reid¹ studied the esterification of benzoic acid by various mercaptans. Reid and Sachs² as well as Kimball and Reid³ have also prepared n-butyl, iso-butyl, sec-butyl and tert-butyl thiol benzoate using alkylating thiol benzoic acid.

Reid and Sachs² also studied the mechanism of the reaction in esterification, and showed conclusively that the hydroxyl group of the acid is eliminated with the proton of the mercaptans as water, also that the reverse reaction starting with the ester and water, yield the oxygen acid and mercaptan as follows:

Faber and Reid⁴ studied the esterification of acetic, propionic and butyric acids by methyl, ethyl, propyl, isobutyl and isoamyl mercaptans. The reaction of mercaptans and thiophenols with carboxylic acids other than the formic acid is analogous to the esterification of alcohols. Robert and Urey⁵ assumed that like alcohols, mercaptans react initially by addition to the double bond of the carboxylic group, it is understandable that the products are thioester and water, rather than the ester and hydrogen sulphide.

The reaction is reversible and the equilibrium unfavourable for the formation of thioester in good yield.

Wenzel and Reid⁶ prepared alkylthiol acetate treating mercaptans with acetic anhydride and aqueous sodium hydroxide. With the mercaptans of higher molecular weight better yields are obtained by using sodium acetate instead of sodium hydroxide.

Mischler⁷ found that an aromatic acid chloride and aliphatic acid chloride also give satisfactory results with mercaptans and aqueous alkali. Holmberg⁸ observed that in the preparation of thioester, pyridine or trimethylamine appears to cause the acylation to occur more smoothly.

Very few optically active aliphatic thioesters were synthesised. In view of this the present work is carried out to synthesise optically active thioesters from S-(+)-2-methylbutan-1-thiol. Treatment of optically active S-(+)-2-methylbutan-1-ol (I), $^{32}\alpha_D -4.62$ ($I = 1$ dm.), with bromine and red phosphorous resulted in S-(+)-2-methyl-1-bromobutane (II), $^{32}\alpha_D +1.69$ ($I = 1$ dm.). It was then treated with thiourea and sodium hydroxide to obtain desired optically active S-(+)-2-methylbutan-1-thiol (III), $^{35}\alpha_D +2.30$ ($I = 1$ dm.), which condensed with the different aliphatic acid chlorides in presence of dry pyridine to obtain various optically active thioesters (IV).

WHERE R = VARIOUS ALKYL GROUP

through 16 inch long column, b.p. 126°-128° optical purity 86%

$$\alpha_{\text{D}}^{32} - 4.62 (l = 1); d_4^{32} 0.8279; n_{\text{D}}^{32} 1.450.$$

S-(+)-2-Methyl-1-bromobutane¹¹ :

It was prepared by bromination of *S*-(-)-2-methyl butan-1-ol (320 g.) with red phosphorous (20.7 g.) and liquid bromine (266.6 g., 86.1 ml.). The resulting *S*-(+)-2-methyl-1-bromobutane was obtained at 116°-118°. Yield 57.3%.

$$\alpha_{\text{D}}^{32} + 1.69 (l = 1); d_4^{32} 1.255; n_{\text{D}}^{32} 1.455.$$

S-(+)-2-Methyl butan-1-thiol :

In a round bottom flask fitted with a condenser *S*-(+)-2-methyl-1-bromobutane (104 g.) and thiourea (80 g.) were refluxed for about 4.5 hr. Solution of sodium hydroxide (30 g.) in water (300 ml.) was added slowly and then refluxed for 2 hr. The cooled reaction mixture was washed twice with water and the organic liquid layer was separated. It was then dried over anhydrous magnesium sulphate and distilled, *S*-(+)-2-Methyl butan-1-thiol was collected at 117°. Yield 52%.

$$\alpha_{\text{D}}^{35} + 2.30 (l = 1); d_4^{35} 1.421; n_{\text{D}}^{35} 1.424.$$

Experimental

S-(-)-2-Methyl butan-1-ol^{9,10} :

The fusel oil contains one of the constituents as optically active *S*-(-)-2-methyl butan-1-ol, which was obtained by repeated fractional distillation

General method for the preparation of optically active aliphatic thioesters:

In a 500 ml. round bottom flask were placed *S*-(+)-2-methyl butan-1-thiol (21 g., 0.2 mole) and pyridine (40 ml.). To the mixture aliphatic acid

TABLE I

No.	Name	R	Yield %	B.P. °C	Sp. rotation α_{D}^{30}	Optically active aliphatic thiol esters of the type $\text{C}_2\text{H}_5-\overset{\text{CH}_3}{\text{CH}}-\text{CH}_2-\text{S}-\text{CO}-\text{R}$		C = O Stretching vibrations $\text{O}=\text{R}-\text{C}-\text{S}-\text{R}'$	% of Calc.	Sulphur Found
						d_4^{30}	n_{D}^{30}			
1.	<i>S</i> -(+)-1-(2-Methylbutyl) thiol-acetate	Methyl	70	176-178	+6.73	0.9828	1.455	1706 cm^{-1} (5.86 μ)	21.96	21.83
2.	<i>S</i> -(+)-1-(2-Methylbutyl) thiol-n-propionate	Ethyl	65	195	+4.25	0.9860	1.452	1709 cm^{-1} (5.85 μ)	20.04	20.18
3.	<i>S</i> -(+)-1-(2-Methylbutyl) thiol-n-butyrate	n-Propyl	62	200	+4.96	0.9842	1.470	1706 cm^{-1} (5.86 μ)	18.42	18.20
4.	<i>S</i> -(+)-1-(2-Methylbutyl) thiol-n-valerate	n-Butyl	72	215	+10.27	0.9815	1.490	1698 cm^{-1} (5.89 μ)	17.05	17.10
5.	<i>S</i> -(+)-1-(2-Methylbutyl) thiol-n-caproate	n-Amyl	59	228-230	-4.25	0.9822	1.471	1709 cm^{-1} (5.85 μ)	15.87	15.92
6.	<i>S</i> -(+)-1-(2-Methylbutyl) thiol-n-heptoate	n-Hexyl	62	238-240	+4.25	1.0680	1.460	1706 cm^{-1} (5.86 μ)	14.84	14.72
7.	<i>S</i> -(+)-1-(2-Methylbutyl) thiol-n-capryloate	n-Heptyl	61	252	+6.02	0.9215	1.461	1706 cm^{-1} (5.86 μ)	13.94	13.80
8.	<i>S</i> -(+)-1-(2-Methylbutyl) thiol-n-caprate	n-Nonyl	62	298-300	+3.54	0.9858	1.458	1709 cm^{-1} (5.85 μ)	12.43	12.39

chloride (0.2 mole) was added dropwise. The contents were refluxed for 1.5 hr on a waterbath. It was then cooled and treated with hydrochloric acid (50%) to remove excess of pyridine. The thiolester extracted with ether, washed with sodium carbonate solution (10%), water and then dried over anhydrous magnesium sulphate and distilled.

Discussion

Looking to the above reactions all the different thiolesters are optically active because in these reactions the asymmetric carbon atom is unaffected. It was observed that in case of these optically active aliphatic thiolesters, with the increase of $-\text{CH}_2$ group there is an irregularity in the optical rotation. In these optically active aliphatic thiolesters, the maximum rotation was found in the case of S-(+)-1-(2-methylbutyl)-thiol-*n*-valerate, $\alpha_D^{30} + 10.27$ ($l = 1$ dm.) and minimum rotation was found in case of S-(+)-1-(2-methylbutyl)-thiol-*n*-caprate, $\alpha_D^{30} + 3.54$ ($l = 1$ dm.). The physical properties including specific rotation and I.R. spectra are recorded in Table 1.

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